

Liquidity Management and Profitability of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The issue of liquidity management is very vital to the existence and survival of any organization especially the deposit money banks. The policy of maintaining adequate liquidity always to meet customer's obligation in the banking sector cannot be over-emphasized. Therefore, this study examines the effect of liquidity management on profitability of listed deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. This study employed correlational research design. The design was employed because it enables an assessment into the nature and extent of relationship between two or more variables. The population comprises all the 14 listed DMBs in Nigeria but was reduced to 12 listed DMBs in Nigeria with the application of filtering technique. Panel data were gathered from secondary sources, specifically from the audited and published annual reports of the DMBs from 2007 to 2020. Panel regression research was employed in analyzing the data where profitability was measured by return on assets (ROA). The results indicate that liquidity management has positive but insignificant effect on Return of Assets of selected banks.

KEYWORDS

Deposit Money Banks, Liquidity Management, Profitability, Nigeria.

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1. Introduction

Profitability is the ability of an organization to generate earnings. The rate or level of the earnings is determined by factors such as liquidity. Liquidity risk arises from the inability of banks to accommodate decreases in liabilities or to fund increases in assets. Inadequate liquidity in a bank can result to insufficient funds; either by increasing liabilities or by promptly converting assets to cash at a reasonable cost. Due to the liquidity challenges and their attendant negative effects on profitability in Nigerian banks two decades ago, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) undertook a re-capitalization excise in the sector in 2005. Consequently, today, the study of liquidity management has become more relevant and pronounced in the subsector. Liquidity represents the capability of a business organization to finance increase in assets and to equally meet required and unforeseen cash and deposit obligations at a reasonable cost and without incurring unacceptable losses (Margaretha & Spartina, 2016; Shaibu & Okafor, 2020). It can be inferred from the foregoing that the composites of liquidity management include cash ratio and loan ratio.

Further, as alluded to by the liquidity preference theory, people require the services of banks to either carry out cash transactions or to store money as wealth (Bibow, 2005). Corroborating this view, shiftability theory adds that banks that cannot meet the transaction needs of their customers from the available cash can convert their assets into cash (Sanni, 2006). As such, banks that have difficulty in meeting customers' cash demand such as loan may experience dwindling profitability as a result of the cash inflow (interest) from the supposed loan. Again, in the event of the customers that have assessed loans defaulting, the bank's profitability is also affected negatively; owing to reduction in the available cash in the bank and increase in losses associated with unpaid interests and/or loaned sum. Moreover, these situations may result to loss of customers' confidence in the bank and/or panic withdrawal.

Research has shown that liquidity management is directly related to effective use of assets (Shekhar & Jena, 2020), while liquidity shortage disrupts the operations of financial institutions, and the relationships with their customers (Shrestha, 2018). It has been reported that liquidity management (current ratio, cash ratio, quick ratio, capital adequacy ratio and interest coverage ratio) is positively and significantly related to profitability (return on equity, return on assets and earnings per share) in financial institutions and manufacturing firms within the period 2006 to 2019 (Afolabi & Williams, 2019; Dadebo & Afolabi, 2020; Fagboyo et al., 2018; Garba, 2020; Malik & Aqeel, 2017; Sinarti & Rahmadany, 2018). The negative and strong relationship between liquidity management (cash-deposit ratio and investment-deposit ratio) and profitability (return on equity) among financial institutions (2011 to 2017) has been established in extant literature (Mishra & Pradhan, 2019; Mohanty & Mehrotra, 2018). Liquidity management (cash to total asset, liquid asset to total assets ratio, loan to total deposit ratio, capital adequacy ratio, liquidity ratio, non-performing loan ratio and interest margin) has been found to have a positive and significant effect on the profitability (return on assets) of financial institutions (2006 and 2017) (Anandasayanan, 2020; Shaibu & Okafor, 2020; Zidan, 2020).

It can thus be deduced from extant literature that plethora of studies relating liquidity management and profitability have been conducted in different parts of the world using various proxies. Also, most of the studies have been situated in financial institutions. However, firstly, similar studies that have utilized secondary data spanning 2007 to 2020 are somewhat nonexistent. Secondly, there is a rarity of related previous studies that focuses on the Nigerian deposit money banks using cash ratio and loan ratio as proxies of liquidity

management and return on assets as dimensions of profitability. This is in spite of the chequered history of the subsector. Specifically, the operations of the Nigerian deposit money banks have been hugely and negatively impacted on by events such as the various reforms and recapitalizations that have been carried on in the subsector. Other factors that influenced the cash and loan ratios of the banks include the global financial crises of 2007-2009, the economic recession suffered by the Nigerian economy between 2015-2016, and of recent the coronavirus 2019 pandemic (code named COVID-19) and its consequential protocols between 2019 to 2021.

Further, since the outcome of this study can be influenced by leverage; the variable will be controlled in the study. This will also be done to limit the influences of confounding and other extraneous variables in the study. Taken together, this study seeks to assess the effect of liquidity management on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Accordingly, the following null hypothesis is formulated and tested in the study:

H₁: Liquidity management has no significant effect on the profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The remaining parts of the paper consist five sections; literature review, methodology, results, discussion and conclusion.

2. Literature Review

This section presents literature relating to profitability, return on assets (ROA), liquidity management, cash ratio, loan ratio and leverage.

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 shows the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable that are examined in the study. The independent variable, liquidity management, is proxied as loan deposit ratio and cash ratio. The proxies of the dependent variable, profitability is return on assets (ROA). ROA is a robust measure of performance (profitability); it is the rate of return earned on the utilization of the asset of the banks. Capital structure management is the control variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the effect of cash ratio and loss ratio on return on assets
Source: Adapted from Ali (2015)

2.1 Profitability

Profitability is a firm's ability and capacity to generate earnings at a rate of sales, level of assets and stock of capital in a specific period (Margaretha & Spartina, 2016). Profit is said to be generated when the income during a given period exceeds the expenses incurred over the same length of time for the sole purpose of generating income (Malik & Aqeel, 2017). The

fundamental requirement is that the income and the expenses must occur during the same period and the income must be a direct consequence of the expenses. The period may be one week, three months or one year (Rufai & Onyeiwu, 2018). Bank profitability therefore is a measure of bank performance. In this study, it is proxied as return on asset (ROA).

2.1.2 Return on Assets

Return on assets (ROA) is an essential indicator normally employed in determining the performance of deposit money banks. The higher the ratio, the better the profitability of banks (Harry, 2015). It is computed by dividing profit after tax by total assets. The ROA shows how banks can generate income from their assets. Notwithstanding, the ROA may be biased because of off-balance sheet activities (Samuel, 2015). However, the principally used variable for determining bank profitability is the ROA because it is not misrepresented by high equity multipliers (Saheed, 2018). The ROA is used in the analysis of profitability in this study.

2.2 Liquidity Management

Liquidity management represent strategies employed by banks to meet deposit and loan demands. These strategies include holding of short-term financial assets (treasury bill and treasury certificate) (Ebhodagbe, 2015). Liquidity management is an on-going process to ensure that cash needs can be met at reasonable cost for a bank to maintain the required level of reserves with the CBN and to meet expected and contingent cash need (Shekhar & Jena, 2020). Liquidity management enable banks compensate for expected and unexpected statement of financial position fluctuation and to provide funds for growth, to accommodate the redemption of deposits and other liabilities and to cover funding increases in the loan and investment portfolio (Samuel, 2015). A minimum operating liquidity level is essential to maintain a comfortable cushion beyond the minimum statutory requirement of 30%, to meet cash needs. A desired target maximum for operating liquidity also needs to be established to reflect the fact that too much liquidity is detrimental to earnings.

From policy perspective, under normal circumstances, double-checking of liquidity ratios and liquidity flows could prove useful in designing a robust prudential approach to liquidity. Liquidity management lays emphasis on the need for daily assessment of the liquidity conditions in banking system, to determine its liquidity needs and thus the volume of liquidity to assign or withdraw from the market. These liquidity needs are defined by the sum of reserve requirements imposed on daily liquidity forecasting of the CBN balance sheet to guide bank's management on the expected level of liquidity in the system over a period from the current period, so that appropriate measures are taken to prevent undesirable market developments, that may negatively impact on the objective of price stability and profitability.

A portfolio of short-term financial securities held by a bank can be easily sold or rediscounted for cash. This approach plus inter-bank borrowings as well as short term accommodation by CBN constitute major sources of liquidity for Nigerian banks. Improved liquidity planning, greater drive for deposits and injection of fresh capital are therefore some available avenues for banks to overcome their liquidity problems. According to Duruechi, Ojiegbe and Otiwu (2016) liquidity measurement entails finding standard or benchmark which each bank should meet to be regarded as being liquid. To obtain a realistic assessment of a bank's liquidity position would require an accurate forecast of cash need and expected level of liquid assets and receipts of cash over a period. The most widely used liquidity

measures are derived from the stock flow or concept, which require the computation of vital ratios.

Abubakar (2015) identified two approaches to liquidity management. These are the stock flow and cash flow approach. The stock flow approach incorporates essential ratio analysis while the cash flow approach emphasizes on the maturity structures of a bank's assets and liabilities and on a measurement of liquidity based on a cash flow concept. The cash flow concept enables the measurement of the extent of the maturity mismatching over a given period with considerable flexibility in determining the conditions under which individual assets or liabilities should be included in specific maturity structures.

The stock flow approach, as the most widely used, considers most importantly the loan-deposit ratio (Nzotta, 2014). Here, all banks' loans are lumped together and then compared with the total deposits as a proxy for total liabilities. A rise in the ratio means a less liquid position and thus the bank(s) would be less inclined to lend and vice-versa. Other prominent ratios notable under the stock flow concept includes the liquidity ratio which relates liquid assets to total deposits, cash reserve ratio. Liquidity management measures using cash ratio. The cash ratio shows a bank's ability to cover its short-term obligations (deposit liabilities) using only cash and cash equivalents. The cash ratio is derived by adding a bank's total reserves of cash and near-cash securities and dividing that sum by its total current liabilities. The cash ratio, sometimes referred to as the cash asset ratio, is a liquidity management metric that indicates a bank's capacity to pay off short-term debt obligations with its cash and cash equivalents. Compared to other liquidity ratios such as the current ratio and quick ratio, the cash ratio is a stricter, more conservative measure because only cash and cash equivalents – a bank's most liquid assets – are used in the calculation.

Another measure of liquidity management is loan to deposit ratio (credit deposit ratio). The ratio of loan and advances to deposits reflects the quantity or proportion of the customers' deposits that has been given out in form of loans and the percentage that is retained in the liquid forms. The ratio serves as a useful planning and control tool in liquidity management since banks use it as a guide in lending and investment, and to make a total evaluation of their expansion program. When the ratio rises to a relatively high level, banks are encouraged to lend and invest and vice versa, to take some benefit of profitability. However, the limitation of the ratio is that it fails to indicate the maturity or quality of the portfolio. It is risky to characterize broad classes of statement of financial position items as more or less liquid than others. Not all assets in any grouping have the same degree of liquidity or maturity. Another limitation of this ratio is that it measures only assets liquidity and excludes any measure of the ability of a bank to raise funds other than through the sale of the assets.

In this study, cash ratio and credit deposit ratio were used as the measure of liquidity management while control with capital structure management. Debt is usually the cheapest source of financing given that debt has a lower cost of funding than equity and is also tax-deductible for a business. However, banks must manage and monitor its debt-to-equity ratio closely so that it will not become over-leveraged. The more highly leveraged a business is, the greater its vulnerability to any downturn in cash flow. This vulnerability becomes even more serious if it coincides with times for debt repayment. A highly leveraged business has less capacity to absorb losses or obtain rollover funds (Aqsa, Kaukab & Naveed, 2021).

2.2.1 Cash Ratio

The cash ratio, sometimes referred to as the cash asset ratio, is a liquidity metric that indicates a company's capacity to pay off short-term debt obligations with its cash and cash equivalents. Compared to other liquidity ratios such as the current ratio and quick ratio, the cash ratio is a stricter, more conservative measure because only cash and cash equivalents of banks' most liquid assets – are used in the calculation (Fagboyo, Adeniran & Adedeji, 2018). The cash ratio is the ratio of cash and cash equivalent to banks' current liabilities. This ratio implies the cash which the bank holds. This ratio determines the credit which can be created from the deposits. Most commonly, the cash ratio is used as a measure of the liquidity of a firm. This measure indicates the willingness of the company to do so without having to sell or liquidate other assets if the company is required to pay its current liabilities immediately. The cash ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures a company's ability to pay off short-term liabilities with highly liquid assets. Compared to the current ratio and the quick ratio, it is a more conservative measure of a company's liquidity position (Mishra & Swain, 2020).

Cash ratio = (Cash + Marketable Securities) / Current Liabilities.

Cash includes legal tender (coins and currency) and demand deposits (cheques, bank drafts, etc.)

Cash equivalents are assets that can be converted into cash quickly. Cash equivalents are readily convertible and subject to insignificant risk. This includes savings accounts, T-bills, and money market instruments. Current liabilities are obligations due within one year. Examples include short-term debt, accounts payable, and accrued liabilities. The cash ratio indicates the amount of cash that the company has on hand to meet its current liabilities. A cash ratio of 0.2 would mean that for every Naira the bank owes creditors in the next 12 months it has 0.2 in cash. 0.2 is considered to be the ideal cash ratio (Garba, 2020).

2.2.2 Loan Ratio

A loan-to-deposit ratio shows a bank's ability to cover loan losses and withdrawals by its customers (Sinarti & Rahmadany, 2018). Investors monitor the LDR of banks to make sure there's adequate liquidity to cover loans in the event of an economic downturn resulting in loan defaults. Also, the LDR helps to show how well a bank is attracting and retaining customers. If a bank's deposits are increasing, new money and new clients are being onboarded. As a result, the bank will likely have more money to lend, which should increase earnings. Although its counterintuitive, loans are an asset for a bank since banks earn interest income from lending. Deposits, on the other hand, are liabilities because banks must pay an interest rate on those deposits, albeit at a low rate. The LDR can help investors determine if a bank is managed properly. If the bank isn't increasing its deposits or its deposits are shrinking, the bank will have less money to lend. In some cases, banks will borrow money to satisfy its loan demand in an attempt to boost interest income. However, if a bank is using debt to finance its lending operations instead of deposits, the bank will have debt servicing costs since it will need to pay interest on the debt.

As a result, a bank that borrows money to lend to its customers will typically have lower profit margins and more debt. A bank would rather use deposits to lend since the interest rates paid to depositors are far lower than the rates it would be charged for borrowing money. The LDR helps investors spot the banks that have enough deposits on hand to lend and won't need to resort to increasing their debt. The proper LDR is a delicate balance for banks. If banks lend too much of their deposits, they might overextend themselves, particularly in an economic downturn. However, if banks lend too few of their deposits, they might have

opportunity cost since their deposits would be sitting on their balance sheets earning no revenue. Banks with low LTD ratios might have lower interest income resulting in lower earnings.

2.3 Leverage

Financial leverage results from using borrowed capital as a funding source when investing to expand the firm's asset base and generate returns on risk capital (Pandey, 2015). Leverage is an investment strategy of using borrowed money specifically, the use of various financial instruments or borrowed capital to increase the potential return of an investment. Leverage is the use of debt (borrowed capital) in order to undertake an investment. The result is to multiply the potential returns from investment. A company can analyze its leverage by seeing what percent of its assets have been purchased using debt. A company can subtract the debt-to-assets ratio by 1 to find the equity-to-assets ratio. If the debt-to-assets ratio is high, a company has relied on leverage to finance its assets. Leverage and liquidity are interrelated as levered company holds liquid assets as a precaution in order to absorb the economic shocks in the market (Oduol, 2011). The regulators and depositors are more concerned with the bank's current debt-paying ability whereas the creditors and other financial institutions are more concerned with company's long-term financial strength. If the banks use the cash to pay down liabilities (the other side of the balance sheet), then they indeed reduce their leverage ratio. But this is not bad as they have lower levels of debt, which is exactly what leverage is about, and are therefore less risky. Banks' liquidity is whether the cash was used to pay back short-term or longer-term liabilities. If the former, then the banks' liquidity ratios are not affected. If the latter, then the banks end up with lower levels of liquidity, which could be problematic.

2.4 Theoretical Review

The underpinning theories for this study are shiftability theory and liquidity preference theory.

2.4.1 Shiftability Theory

Shiftability theory states that the level of defensible financial institution liquidity management is having possession or investing in legal capital capable of shifting solely to other investments in obtaining liquid equipment. Loan for instance becomes secondary back up while secondary back up shifts to become primary back up. This means Shiftability theory suggests that financial institutions should give credit paid with notification before they apply for commercial paper pawn. According to this theory banks maintain liquidity if they hold assets that are marketable. During a liquidity crisis such assets are easily converted into cash. Thus, this theory contends that shiftability, or marketability or transferability of bank assets is a basis for ensuring good liquidity management (Sanni, 2006). Supposing when there are no hard cash, financial institutions tend to sell pawn goods on loan aiming to obtain adequate cash. The friction happens because collateral which is illiquid turns into liquid. Besides this they also often sell marketable securities like super common stock. As a result, the shiftability theory is comprehended to give description and confidence of management of financial institutions until certain degree of removable asset possession in condition is needed to fulfill liquidity management (Rufai & Onyeiwu, 2018).

2.4.2 Liquidity Preference Theory

According to Bibow (2005) liquidity preference theory states that people value money for both the transaction of Current business and its use as a store of wealth. Thus, they will sacrifice the ability to earn interest on money that they want to spend in the present, and that they want to have it on hand as a precaution. When interest rates increase, they become

willing to hold less money for these purposes to secure a profit. Also, according to Elgar (1999), the need for money is to finance expenditure plans or is speculating on the future path of the interest rate, or, finally, because one is uncertain about what the future may have in store. So, it is advisable to hold some fraction of one's resources in the form of pure purchasing power. These motives became known as transactions-, speculative and precautionary motives to demand money. The banks' liquidity preference approach suggests that banks pursue active balance sheet policies instead of passively accommodating the demand for credit. This study adopted liquidity preference theory.

2.5 Empirical Review

Malik and Aqeel (2017) conducted an investigation into the relationship between liquidity management and profitability of commercial banks in Pakistan. Profitability was denoted by return on equity and Return on Asset, while liquidity management was proxy by current ratio, capital ratio, credit facilities and liquid assets ratio. Data was collected from the financial statement from the sampled banks in Pakistan. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design using data from the period between 2004 and 2013. The secondary data gathered was examined using correlation and regression model. The result provided evidence that Current ratio has a positive and strong impact on return on equity and Return on Asset. Furthermore, the study revealed that liquid assets ratio has a negative relationship with return on equity and Return on Asset.

Aziz et al. (2017) examined the effects of liquidity management on the amount of profitability of firms in Iraq. The study involved financial reports from financial institutions resident in Iraq. The study adopted a quantitative research design utilizing data from the period between 2008 and 2018. The secondary data gathered was analyzed using Simple linear regression analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis. The study showed that Capital/Risk Weighted Assets has a positive and significant impact on Return on Assets. In addition, the result also found that Assets/Shareholders Equity, Market Rate of Interest and Bank Size have a negative and significant relationship with Return on Assets.

Shrestha (2018) carried out an empirical examination on the effect of liquidity management on the measures of profitability, which was denoted by Return on Assets. Cash Reserve ratio, Credit Deposit Ratio and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study used published annual reports from financial institutions based in Nepal. The study adopted a panel research design using data from the period between 2012 and 2016. The secondary data collected was examined using panel regression model. The results of the analysis suggested that Cash Reserve ratio, and Credit Deposit Ratio have a positive and substantial relationship with Return on Assets.

Sinarti and Rahmadany (2018) explored the effect of liquidity management on the size of profitability of financial institutions in Indonesia. Quick ratio and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved a survey of published annual reports from financial institutions based in Indonesia. The study adopted a panel research design utilizing data from the period between 2006 and 2019. The secondary data gathered was examined using simple regression analysis. The study revealed Quick ratio has a positive and significant impact on profitability.

Fagboyo et al. (2018) investigated the effects of liquidity management on the degree of profitability of firms listed in Nigeria. Profitability was represented by Return on Equity and

Return on Assets. Quick ratio, cash ratio, liquidity coverage ratio and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study used financial statement from deposit money banks situated in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design utilizing data from 2007 to 2016. The secondary data sourced was analyzed using multiple linear regressions. The results indicated that quick ratio, has a positive and significant relationship with Return on Equity and Return on Assets. On the other hand, the study reveals that cash ratio; liquidity coverage ratio has a negative and significant relationship with Return on Equity and Return on Assets. This study did cover the impact of COVID-19; therefore, current study filled the gap.

Shrestha (2018) carried out an empirical examination on the effect of liquidity management on the measures of profitability, which was denoted by Return on Assets. Cash Reserve ratio, Credit Deposit Ratio and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study used published annual reports from financial institutions based in Nepal. The study adopted a panel research design using data from the period between 2012 and 2016. The secondary data collected was examined using panel regression model. The results of the analysis suggested that cash Reserve ratio and Credit Deposit Ratio have a positive and substantial relationship with Return on Assets.

Sinarti and Rahmadany (2018) explored the effect of liquidity management on the size of profitability of financial institutions in Indonesia. Quick ratio and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved a survey of published annual reports from financial institutions based in Indonesia. The study adopted a panel research design utilizing data from the period between 2006 and 2019. The secondary data gathered was examined using simple regression analysis. The study revealed Quick ratio has a positive and significant impact on profitability.

Onyekwelu et al. (2018) examined the effect of liquidity on financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study sample was five (5) deposit money banks in Nigeria. Secondary data were collected from the firms for ten years period from 2007- 2016. The data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. Results showed that liquidity has positive and significant effect on banks' profitability ratios and recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria should review and monitor the effectiveness of liquidity policy tools in banks and placed appropriate sanctions on erring banks to ensure effective implementation of these policy tools to achieve desired liquidity level.

Mohanty and Mehrotra (2018) examined empirically the relationship between liquidity management and profitability, which was represented by Return on Assets and Return on Equity. Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio and Investment-Deposit Ratio were adopted as proxies for liquidity management. The study sampled financial statement from banking sector operating in India. The study adopted a quantitative panel model using data from the period between 2011 and 2015. The secondary data collected was analyzed using panel regression model. The empirical result suggested that Cash-Deposit Ratio, and Investment-Deposit Ratio have a negative and substantial effect on Return on Assets. In addition, the findings showed that Cash-Deposit Ratio and Credit-Deposit Ratio had no significant impact on Return on Equity.

Afolabi and Williams (2019) assessed the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria in relations to liquidity management. Data was sourced from the financial reports of fifteen

listed DMBs Nigeria for the period of ten years (2009-2018). The independent variable for the study was liquidity management proxied by current ratio, cash ratio, quick ratio, capital adequacy ratio and interest coverage ratio, while returns on asset, returns on equity and earnings per share have been used as proxies for performance as dependent variable. Panel least square was used for data analysis with 5% level of significance. The result of the study revealed that liquidity management has a positive effect on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and therefore recommends that the regulators should set up board of professionals to oversee liquidity management amongst DMBs in the country, on a regular basis to avoid liquidity problem that may ruin the banks.

Mishra and Pradhan (2019) explored the effect of liquidity management on the proportion of profitability, which was denoted by Return on Assets and Return on Equity. Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio and Investment-Deposit Ratio was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved published annual reports from private banks based in India. The study adopted a quantitative research design utilizing data from the period between 2013 and 2017. The secondary data collected was examined using panel regression model. Results of the regression analysis displayed that Cash-Deposit Ratio, and Investment-Deposit Ratio has a negative and strong impact on Return on Assets. Furthermore, the result also found that Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, and Investment-Deposit Ratio have no significant effect on Return on Equity.

Ali and Jameel (2019) carried out an empirical investigation on the effect of liquidity management on the measures of profitability of banks in Iraq. The study focused on financial reports from deposit money banks situated in Iraq. The study adopted a quantitative research design utilizing data from the period between 2006 and 2016. The secondary data gathered was analyzed using pooled regression model. The findings showed that liquidity management has a negative and insignificant relationship with Return on Asset and Return on Equity.

Pradhan and Gautam (2019) focused on identifying the effect of liquidity management on the profitability of firms in Nepal. The study focused on financial statement from banking sector operating in Nepal. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design using data from the period between 2009 and 2015. The secondary data collected was examined using panel regression model. The results of the regression analysis suggested that capital ratio, investment ratio, cash ratio, have a positive and strong association with Return on Assets. However, the result revealed that liquid asset ratio has a negative and substantial effect on Return on Assets.

Zidan (2020) focused on providing evidence on the impact of liquidity management on the profitability of Palestinian firms. Profitability was denoted by Return on Assets. Loans to Deposits ratio was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved a survey of published annual reports from financial institutions based in Palestine. The study adopted a panel research design using data from the period between 2008 and 2017. The secondary data sourced was analyzed using panel regression model. The study revealed that Loans to Deposits ratio has a significant effect on Return on Assets.

Shaibu and Okafor (2020) investigated the impact of liquidity management on profitability of financial institutions in Nigeria. Cash ratio, cash to total asset, cash to total deposit ratio, liquid asset to total assets ratio and loan to total deposit ratio were adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved financial statement from financial institutions

based in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design utilizing data from the period between 2006 and 2016. The secondary data collected was analyzed using correlation and regression analysis. The findings showed that cash to total asset, liquid asset to total assets ratio and loan to total deposit ratio have a positive and significant association with Return on Asset. On the other hand, the findings showed liquid asset to total assets ratio has a negative and substantial impact on Return on Asset. Also, the findings showed that the relationship between cash ratio and loan to total deposit is positive but insignificant. Anandasayanan (2020) conducted an empirical study on the impact of liquidity management on the rate of profitability of financial institutions in Sri Lanka. The dependent variable was Return on Asset while, capital adequacy ratio, liquidity ratio, non-performing loan ratio, and interest margin were the proxy for liquidity management. The study focused on published annual reports from financial institutions resident in Sri Lanka. The study adopted a panel research design using data from the period between 1998 and 2017. The secondary data gathered was examined using regression analysis. The result suggested that capital adequacy ratio, liquidity ratio, non-performing loan ratio, and interest margin has a positive and significant relationship with Return on Asset.

Dadepo and Afolabi (2020) empirically evaluate the relationship between liquidity management and the amount of profitability of banks in Nigeria. Quick and cash ratios and was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study used financial reports from banking sector operating in Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative research design utilizing data from the period between 2012 and 2016. The secondary data sourced was analyzed using correlation and regression analyses. Results indicated that cash ratio has a negative but significant effect on Return on Asset. Furthermore, the study reveals that quick and cash ratios has a positive and insignificant relationship with Return on Asset. Garba (2020) conducted a study on liquidity management and the extent of profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. cash ratio and quick ratio were adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study involved published annual reports from manufacturing firms operating in Nigeria. The study adopted a panel research design using data from the period between 2008 and 2017. The secondary data sourced was examined using correlation and regression model. The study found that cash ratio has a positive and substantial association with profitability. Furthermore, the study reveals that quick ratio has a negative and insignificant relationship with profitability.

Mishra and Swain (2020) investigated empirical evidence for the predicted relationship between liquidity management and the measures of profitability in India. Cash Deposit Ratio, Cash Deposit Ratio, Investment Deposit Ratio, Term Loans to Total Advances and Savings Bank Deposit to Total Deposits was adopted as proxy for liquidity management. The study used financial statement from deposit money banks operating in India. The study adopted an ex-post factor research design using data from the period between 2005 and 2018. The secondary data gathered was examined using correlation matrix and panel regression analysis. The study's findings revealed that Cash Deposit Ratio, Cash Deposit Ratio, Investment Deposit Ratio, Term Loans to Total Advances and Savings Bank Deposit to Total Deposits have a strong effect on Return on Asset and Return on Equity. Aqsa et al. (2021) investigated Impact of financial leverage on firm's profitability of banking sector of Pakistan. Convenient sampling technique was adopted to ascertain the impact of firms' profitability on the data gathered from annual reports of 10 private banks from 2007 – 2016. Profitability was proxied with return on asset and return on equity. EViews system was used to regress the model. From the analysis, it was revealed that there is a significant relationship between return on

assets, return on equity with leverages which means that financial leverages have a significant impact on firm’s profitability. Adeel, Ibrahim and Sayed (2021) examined the impact of financial leverage on profitability of recapitalized banks in Ghana over the period 2008-2017. The random effects and fixed effects estimation approaches was adopted. It was revealed that leverage has a significant negative effect on banks’ profits regardless of the proxy of profitability. Based on the findings, the study concluded that financial leverage is detrimental to banks' profit growth in Ghana. It is evident from extant literature that previous results are inconclusive and inconsistent. Also, there are period gaps and exclusion of major event in the operating of environment of the deposit money banks (Nigeria) such COVID 19 and inappropriate recommendations. Hence, there is need to conduct this study to fill and address the limitations.

3. Methodology

This section focused on the methodology used in this study which includes research design, population and sampling design, data collection methods, data analysis methods and testing of data validity and reliability. Finally, this section presented the model adopted in the study to be able to analyze and discuss the solution to the research hypotheses and arrive at conclusions. The design of this research is correlation because it enables an assessment into the nature and extent of relationship between two or more variables. In this case, correlational research design provides a basis for understanding the relationship between liquidity management and profitability. The design was appropriate as it sought to ascertain the effect of liquidity management on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The population of this study is all the listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Filtering application was adopted to select the actual population studied. For an individual DMB to qualify, it must be in operation throughout the set period of study and with availability of data. After applying filters, the actual population was reduced to 12 DMBs representing 85.7% of listed banks on Nigerian Exchange group as of 31st December 2020. The filtering criteria is based on the following: all banks must be listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX Group) from 1st January 2007 to 31st December 2020: data must be available and uniform within the period of study and the DMBs must have the same reporting currency related variables for measurement. The variables used for the study are clearly defined with their measurement stated in the Table 2.

Table 1. *Study Population and Sample Size frame*

SN	Deposit Money Banks	Sample Size	Year of Listing	Sector
1	Access Bank Plc.	•	1998	Banking
2	Ecobank Transnational Incorporated	•	2006	Banking
3	Fidelity Bank Plc	•	2005	Banking
4	First Bank Holding	•	1969	Banking
5	First City Monumental Bank	•	2004	Banking
6	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc.	•	1996	Banking
7	Jaiz Bank Plc	•	2017	Banking
8	Stanbic IBTC Holdings Plc	•	2005	Banking
9	Sterling Bank Plc.	•	1983	Banking
10	Union Bank Nig.Plc.	•	1970	Banking
11	United Bank for Africa Plc	•	1970	Banking
12	Unity Bank Plc	•	2003	Banking
13	Wema Bank Plc.	•	1974	Banking
14	Zenith Bank Plc	•	2004	Banking

Source: Nigerian Exchange Website (2020).

This study employed secondary data collection. This study variables were deduced from audited financial statements of the listed DMBs in Nigeria for the financial periods 2007 to 2020. Data was collected for the listed DMBs in Nigeria in operation during the period and this ensured completeness and consistency of the study elements. This study used multiple linear regression equation and the method of estimation was Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to establish the relationship between liquidity and profitability exists between the study

variables. To achieve the objectives of this study, a model was developed using profitability as the dependent variable and liquidity as the independent variable followed by data analysis and interpretation of the results. The model used in the study is:

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1LOR_{i,t} + \beta_2CAR_{i,t} + \beta_3LEV_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

ROA represents Return on Assets for bank *i* at time *t*, LOR represents Loan Ratio for bank *i* at time *t*, CAR represents Cash Ratio for bank *i* at time *t*, LEV represents Leverage for bank *i* at time *t*, β_0 = Intercept, β_1 and β_3 = Coefficient Parameters, *i* = 1 to 12 banks, *t* = 2007-2020, ϵ = Error term.

The statistical analysis techniques include descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. Multicollinearity was checked using a correlation matrix. Multicollinearity occurs if two or more independent variables are highly correlated with one another. Multicollinearity is said to exist between two variables if they have a Pearson correlation value greater than 0.8. Variance inflation factor (VIF) test was to check how the independent variables have multicollinearity with each other thus, if the centered VIF or mean MIF is less than 10, it therefore means that they do not have multicollinearity problem but otherwise, they have multicollinearity problem. Furthermore, normality test is conducted using Shapiro-wilk normality test while hausman test was conducted to test for panel effects. The selection between the fixed and random model was aided by Hausman specification Result whose Hausman specification p-value is less than 5% level of confidence, fixed effect model is more appropriate but where it is greater than 5% level of confidence Random model is more suitable. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the significance of the model, The significance of the regression model was determined at 95% confidence interval and 5% level of significance. Adjusted R squared was used to determine the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variables.

Table 2

Types, Variables Definitions, Measurements and Sources

Type	Variable	Measurement	Definition	Source
Dependent	Return on assets	Profit before tax to total assets	ROA shows how banks can generate income from their assets. The higher ratio indicates good to the stakeholders of the banks on their interest invested	Herry, 2015 & Mustapha (2017)
Independent	Loan Ratio	Loan and advances to Total Deposits	The ratio of loan and advances to deposits reflects the quantity or proportion of the customers' deposits that has been given out in form of loans and the percentage that is retained in the liquid forms.	Pruential Guidelines (2010) and Ali & Jameel (2019)
Independent	cash ratio	Cash and cash equivalent to current liabilities	cash ratio is a measure of a bank's short-term solvency and is calculated by dividing cash and cash equivalent by current liabilities. A cash ratio that is greater than one is adjudged satisfactory	Wachira, Gregory and Fred (2017)
Control	Leverage ratio	Total debt to total equity	This reveals the portion of debt financing in the capital structure of the bank. Higher ratios reveal gearing while low ratio shows more of equity financing	Olha, Viktoriia and Roksolana (2018)

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2021).

4. Results and Discussion

This section provides the results of descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, diagnostic test and test of hypothesis formulated for this study.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2 where the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviations of the variables used in the study are shown.

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
ROA	168	0.033	0.606	-0.124	0.531
CAR	168	1.855	4.676	0.057	45.590
LOR	168	0.674	0.405	0.013	5.143
LEV	168	7.249	15.389	0.001	191.210

Source: Result Output from STATA 15.1

The Stata 15.1 output presented in Table 3 show that there are 168 observations. Return on Assets (ROA), which is the ratio of profit before tax to total assets, shows a mean of 0.033. The positive value implies that for every ₦1 invested in the selected deposit money banks, N0.03 is gain from that investment. The standard deviation of 0.606 in terms of ROA signifies that there is a wide dispersion of the data from the mean because standard deviation is higher than the mean value. The data analysis on ROA also shows that the minimum amount of lost from every N1 invested is N0.12, while the maximum amount gained from every N1 invested is N0.53. Table 3 also shows the detailed results of the descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables respectively. The most prominent among the results in the descriptive statistics are the higher standard deviations of LEV (15.389) and lowest standard deviation of LOR (0.405).

From Table 3, it is shown that CAR, LOR, and LEV have mean values of 1.855, 0.674 and 7.249 respectively with average survival score of 3.259. The DMBs experienced a high growth rate in their cash ratio up to a maximum of 45.59 and a minimum of 0.057. This is an indication that the DMBs sometimes have more of their assets in carryout their transaction in the case of high CAR and trading more with their customers' money in the case of the low CAR. The DMBs leverage from 0.00 to 191.21 with a mean value of 7.249 and a standard deviation of 15.389. The standard deviation of the leverage far higher than its mean is due to the wide dispersion of the leverage data over time.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

Table 4 below displays the correlation values between regressor and the regressed and the relationship between the independent variables themselves. The values are gotten from the Pairwise correlation of two-tailed significance. It shows the correlation matrix with the top values displaying the Pairwise correlation coefficient showing the two-tailed significance of these coefficients.

Table 4
Pearson Pairwise Correlation Matrix of the Sampled Observations

	ROA	CAR	LOR	LEV
ROA	1.0000			
CAR	0.0372	1.0000		
LOR	0.0006	-0.0636	1.0000	
LEV	-0.0925	-0.0649	-0.0629	1.0000

Source: Result Output from STATA 15.1

Table 4 shows the correlation results between liquidity management variables (CAR, LOR, and LEV) and the profitability (ROA) of the listed DMBs in Nigeria. The table result shows that LEV is negatively related with ROA from the correlation coefficient of 0.0925 which is significant at 5% level of significance. This indicates that the profitability (ROA) of listed DMBs has negative association with liquidity (LEV). This may be due to interest rates and other loan servicing conditions the DMBs embark on monthly or yearly. This is evidenced from Table 4 that LEV reduces DMBs ROA significantly. The table shows that there is a positive relationship between CAR and LOR with the profitability (ROA) of listed DMBs from the correlation coefficient of 0.0372 and 0.0006 respectively which CAR is insignificant at 5% level of significance.

Furthermore, in Table 4, DMBs’ ability to manage their CAR rent assets is positively related to ROA up to 3.72% than any other liquidity variables in this study. The negative correlation of the liquidity variable, LEV is that indication that DMBs have poor management of the borrowed fund in their businesses and lead to the decrease of their profits. Following the analysis of the relationships between liquidity of firm survival (CAR, LOR, and LEV) and profitability (ROA) of the listed DMBs in Nigeria, the study in the following section presents and discusses the regression results of the model of the study from which the hypotheses of the study are tested and the relevant inferences are drawn about the relationship between liquidity and the profitability of listed DMBs in Nigeria.

4.3 Diagnostic Tests

For better validity and reliability of all statistical inferences to be drawn for the study, this section presents the result of the diagnostic test conducted. Shapiro-Wilk W Test for normal data was conducted and it was found that the data used for the study are not normally distributed as it revealed significant p-value (See appendix B). Similarly, Multicollinearity Test was conducted to check whether there is a strong correlation between the independent variables which could mislead the result of the study. The result of the diagnostics test reveals no multicollinearity in the data. The variance inflation factor and the tolerance were found to be consistently lower than ten and one respectively indicating the absence of multicollinearity (see appendix B). Heteroscedasticity Test evidenced from Breuch Pagan/Cook-Weisberg coefficient of 3.17 with a p-value of 0.3664 confirms the presence of the effects of heteroskedasticity for the model, that is, there is constant variance in the residuals.

4.4 Regression Results

The regression results of the model described in section 3 is presented and interpreted below.

Table 5

Regression Results (OLS)

ROA	Coefficient	p-value
Constant	0.0339	0.003
CAR	0.0082	0.691
LOR	-0.0005	0.968
LEV	-0.0004	0.247
Prob > F	0.6644	
R-squared	0.0095	
Adjusted R-squared	-0.0086	

Source: Regression Result Output from STATA 15.1

4.4.1 Interpretation of Regression Result

The regressed coefficient correlation result in table 6 shows the existence of a positive and statistically significant relationship between CAR, LOR, and LEV ($\beta_0=0.0339$), and ROA at 5% significance level. The probability values for the slope coefficient show that $P(x_1=0.6644 > 0.05)$. This implies that liquidity has a statistically significant relationship with ROA at 5% significance level. The coefficient of determination obtained is -0.01 (-1%), which is commonly referred to as the value of adjusted R^2 . The cumulative test of hypothesis using adjusted R^2 to draw statistical inference about the explanatory variables employed in this regression equation, shows that the adjusted R-Squared value shows that -1% of the systematic variations in the dependent variable can be jointly predicted by all the independent variables. 101% was explained by leverage issue and some unknown variables that were not included in the model. The overall significance of the model Prob > F-statistic (0.6644) is statistically significant at 5%. The results translated to the formulated model as:

$$ROA = 0.0339 + 0.0082CAR - 0.0005LOR - 0.0004LEV$$

The result shows that a unit increase in CAR rent ratio will lead to a corresponding 0.0082 increase in ROA of the listed DMBs in Nigeria holding all other factors constant. Based on the finding, the study accepts the null hypothesis and concluded that CAR rent ratio of listed DMBs in Nigeria has no significant effect on their profitability. This result confirms the findings from Anandasayanan (2020) in Sri Lanka who found that CAR rent ratio has no significant positive effect on profitability of banks. The finding is however contrary to the results of Malik and Aqeel (2017) in Pakistan, Pradhan, and Gautam (2019) in Nepal, and Afolabi and Williams (2019) in Nigeria which revealed that the positive effect of CAR rent ratio on profitability of banks is statistically significant.

In relation to the second measure of liquidity management –loan ratio (LOR) the results indicated that loan ratio has no significant effect on the profitability of DMBs in Nigeria ($\beta = -0.0005$, $p = 0.968$). The implication is that a unit increase in LOR will lead to a corresponding 0.0005 decrease in ROA. However, the decrease is not statistically significant. It should be noted here that the DMBs will incur lost whenever the LEV is added becomes insolvent. In view of the forgoing H_0 which states that liquidity management has no significant effect on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria is accepted.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The objective of this study is to examine the effect of liquidity management on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. In view of the findings, this study concludes that CAR rent ratio, loan ratio and leverage have negative relationship with the return on assets (ROA) but not significant effect on Return of Assets. In line with objective of the study, the formulated hypothesis which says that liquidity management has no significant effect on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria is accepted. Leverage negatively correlated with ROA but does not have significant effect on ROA of the selected banks in Nigeria. Therefore, this study recommends that the management of deposit money banks in Nigeria should improve on cash ratio, loan ratio and reduce their leverage from high gearing to low gearing in order to boost their profitability. It also recommends that any decision of the DMBs to borrow more money to purchase non-current assets of high amount should be discouraged totally since this decision will affect the going concern of DMBs in Nigeria.

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